

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PROCESS OF STUDENTS' LEARNING AT SCHOOL

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Abstract

When teaching at school, the main role in the education of schoolchildren is played by social and psychological factors. This work involves the student's senses, sensations, perception, then memorization and the formation of associations, comprehension and creative processing of information. Emotional processes ensure a person's selective attitude to different aspects of reality. Decision-making processes are of great importance. The main moment of decision-making is the choice of an action option that allows achieving the best result. Control processes are reduced to two main blocks: evaluative processes and processes preceding the action.

Keywords: education, school, social, psychological, student, training, attention, memory, thinking, process, factor.

Subject, goals and objectives:

The attention of a student is a process that connects the psychoregulatory and cognitive spheres of the psyche and allows for the selectivity of reflection, processing and memorization of information. Thinking is a process that connects the present, past and future. Language is a system of signs or acoustic images that correlates with a system of concepts [2;4]. A linguistic sign – a word – is a unity of the signifier and the signified. Subjective meanings of words are called senses. Non-verbal means of speech behavior include voice intonation, pitch, timbre, and volume. The most general formal-dynamic characteristic of a student's individual behavior is his temperament, which mainly includes activity, emotionality, flexibility, and pace of activity. Abilities have an individual degree of expression. Abilities are not limited to the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities, but affect the ease and speed of mastering them. Abilities are special and general: special abilities are related to individual subsystems of the psyche, and general abilities are related to the psyche as an integral system. The psychological formula for successful learning of a student consists of a combination of motivation, information search, its understanding and memorization, application of information, and systematicity of classes [1;3].

Teaching schoolchildren with special educational needs, as well as the education system for ordinary children, is a holistic system consisting of logically connected links: perception of educational material; consolidation of educational material; application of acquired knowledge and skills.

The beginning of the cognitive activity of children with special educational needs is how much the child perceives the proposed material. The child's perception is closely connected with the ideas formed as a result of previous perceptions and thinking. The perception of the material by our children is imperfect. Most often, perception becomes fragmentary, often there is no necessary semantic connection, in addition, there is no connection between perceptions and ideas, perception and thinking. Due to the presence of these features of the

process of perception of educational material by children, specialists use special techniques and means aimed at ensuring completeness, accuracy and adequacy of reality [5;7].

Particular attention is paid to teaching children to analyze the results of their perceptions, compare the perceived with the sample.

Consolidation of knowledge and skills in practical activities. Constant and thorough consolidation of knowledge of educational material by children is an extremely important link in training due to the presence of serious violations of the processes of memorization and reproduction in children. Considering the fact that the visual material is retained in children's memory for the longest time, and vice versa, all sorts of verbal generalizations quickly disappear from memory, the consolidation of educational material is based on visual-figurative, emotional memory with a gradual transition to verbal-logical memorization. In the process of repetition, the acquired knowledge is clarified, it is possible to correct and replenish it, help in the correctness of the acquired knowledge and methods of action. All this creates favorable conditions for the application of knowledge and skills in practice [3;7].

Application of knowledge and skills in practical activities. Difficulties in mastering the skills of applying knowledge and skills, of course, are largely associated with the presence of defects, however, many of them are overcome or significantly reduced in the learning process. This is facilitated by the presence of such conditions as:

- 1) maintaining the unity of assimilation and application of knowledge;
- 2) strengthening the connection of learning with life, practice;
- 3) systematic involvement of children in practical activities that require the use of acquired knowledge.

The problem of the success of school education is very complex, and its in-depth consideration requires a comprehensive approach using knowledge from different fields of science: general and developmental psychology, pedagogy, physiology. There are three main

factors that influence the success of school education: the psychological and pedagogical factor, the neuro-psychological factor, and the psychological factor. Further in my speech I will tell you how these factors influence the success

A factor that significantly influences the success of children's acquisition of knowledge, and therefore their academic performance, is the psychological and pedagogical factor, the components of which are the age of the child beginning systematic education at school, and the didactic and methodological system (developmental education system) within which school education will be carried out [4;6].

It is impossible to dispute that education should be consistent with the child's level of development. In order to clarify the real relationship of the development process to learning opportunities, it is necessary to determine at least two levels of child development: the first is the level of actual development (this is a set of skills that the child possesses at the present moment in time) and the second is the zone of proximal development (it determines functions that have not yet matured, but are in the process of maturation, which will mature tomorrow, which are now still in their infancy. A greater or lesser possibility of a child's transition from what he can do independently to what he can do in cooperation characterizes the dynamics of his development and the success of mental activity.) Despite the recognition of the important role of education in the processes of mental development, school curricula for many years were oriented towards the level of the child's actual development. Dissatisfaction with this situation led many scientists and methodologists to develop developmental curricula for elementary schools. The difference between developmental programs is that a zone of proximal development of schoolchildren is created on the basis of the basic laws of mental development. This means that in the process of acquiring knowledge, a number of internal development processes are set in motion that would be impossible without such training. As a result, the development of students rises to a higher level.

While mental development has a significant impact on school performance, it does not always clearly determine a child's success or failure in school. In middle and high school, other factors begin to have a strong influence on the success of school education, blurring the influence of the mental development factor. In other words, a direct connection between the level of a student's mental development and the average grade of his school performance is not always confirmed in school practice. This means that a child with a low level of mental development can study quite well, and a student who shows high results on intelligence tests can demonstrate average or below average success in learning. This indicates a variety of reasons that give rise to

school failure, where the level of mental development is only one of them.

Conclusions:

The next factor influencing the success of school education, which determines a number of school difficulties, is psychological readiness for school education. What is meant by psychological readiness of children for school education? We are talking about a radical restructuring of the child's entire lifestyle and activity, about the transition to a new stage of development, which is associated with profound changes in the child's entire inner world, which cover all areas of the child's personality. Readiness for school education means achieving a certain level of development of cognitive abilities, personal qualities, socially significant needs, interests, motives.

The main condition for the formation of psychological readiness for school is the full satisfaction of the needs of each child in the game. It is in the game, as is known, that all cognitive processes of the child are formed, the ability to arbitrarily control their behavior, obeying the rules set by the game roles, all psychological neoplasms of the preschool period of development are formed and the prerequisites for the transition to a new qualitative level of development are laid. However, in life, especially in recent years, an alarming situation has developed with the psychological unpreparedness of a large number of children coming to study in the 1st grade. One of the reasons for this negative phenomenon is the fact that modern preschoolers not only play little, but also do not know how to play. This distorts the normal path of mental development and negatively affects the formation of children's readiness for school. One of the reasons for this is the incorrect understanding by parents and educators of the preparation of children for school. Instead of providing the child with the best conditions for the development of his play activity, adults, taking time away from play activities and artificially accelerating the child's development, teach him to write, read and count, that is, those educational skills and abilities that the child must master in the next period of age development.

References

1. Çələbiyev M.Z. Uşaq psixologiyası. Bakı: 2015
2. Əmrahlı L.S., Rzayeva N.T. Uşaq psixologiyası. Bakı: 2010
3. Həmzəyev M. Yaş və pedaqoji psixologiyanın əsasları. Bakı: 2003
4. Qədirov Ə.Ə. Yaş psixologiyası. Bakı: 2002
5. Quliyev E. Kiçik məktəblilərin psixologiyası. Bakı: 2003
6. Mehdizadə Z.M. Psychology. I – II – III editions. Bakı: 1982, 1984, 1988
7. Dubrovina I.V., Lisina M.I. Age-related features of children's mental development. Moscow: 1982